

Managing Editor's Column

Vol. 2, No. 1; January 28, 1996

Dear Readers:

Hi, everyone and welcome to the start of the second volume of J.UCS! This first issue contains three papers from, again, rather different areas. I hope you will continue to enjoy the mixture of information J.UCS is providing.

The CD-ROM with the first volume of J.UCS is now under production. If you want a copy (free of charge) please send an email to Springer Pub. Co. Heidelberg (schies@springer.de): we will start shipping CD-ROM's in March, and will continue to do so as long as supplies last. So, if you want to make sure to get a copy, please send in your "order" including mailing address immediately.

The printed version of the first volume of J.UCS is also under preparation, but is not expected to be available before April 96. I will mention in this column when it is available.

For now, all the best,

Yours sincerely,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Hermann Maurer
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